

Employee Satisfaction with Facilities Management Services in a Nigerian Private University: Evidence from Covenant University, Ota

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Abstract

This study assessed employee satisfaction with facilities management services in higher educational facilities at Covenant University, Ota, focusing on staff of the College of Management and Social Sciences and the College of Leadership and Development Studies. A quantitative research method was adopted using an exploratory survey design and a structured questionnaire. From a population of 199 employees, selected purposively because they are directly involved in or affected by facilities services, making them appropriate for evaluating satisfaction levels, a sample size of 133 was determined at a 95% confidence level and 5% margin of error, with 121 valid responses retrieved for analysis. The questionnaire captured respondents' socio-demographic characteristics and perceptions of facilities management services using closed-ended Likert scale items. Data were analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences [SPSS], employing frequencies, percentages, mean scores, and the Relative Agreement Index [RAI]. Findings indicate that the respondents were largely professionally mature and highly educated, with 85.1% possessing qualifications above HND or B.Sc., 73.6% being teaching staff, and 67.8% occupying private offices. Awareness of facilities management services was generally high, enabling informed evaluations of service performance. High levels of satisfaction were recorded for car parking [mean = 4.00, RAI = 0.80], cleaning and waste management [mean = 3.94, RAI = 0.79], and water supply [mean = 3.92, RAI = 0.78], reflecting effective delivery of routine and visible services. Lower satisfaction levels were observed for termite treatment [mean = 2.84, RAI = 0.57], civil works [mean = 3.06, RAI = 0.61], and mechanical services such as air conditioning and plumbing [mean = 3.16, RAI = 0.63]. The frequency of complaints further showed that mechanical works ranked highest [mean = 3.55, RAI = 0.71], followed by civil works [mean = 3.36, RAI = 0.67] and cleaning services [mean = 3.11, RAI = 0.62]. The study concludes that while performance is strong in routine facilities services, improvements are required in technical and preventive maintenance to enhance overall employee satisfaction and institutional productivity.

Keywords: *Facilities management, facilities, facilities services, employee satisfaction, university*

INTRODUCTION

Potkany et al (2015) posited that facilities management (FM) is a term that is closely associated with building management. They assert that facilities management should not only be understood as general building management connected with everyday building operations, but it should also include long-term planning with a focus on

its users. According to Adewunmi-Abolarinwa (2024), the International Facility Management Association (IFMA) defined facilities management as a method which task in organizations is to mutually harmonize employees, work activities and the work environment that includes principles of business administration,

architecture and humanities, and technical sciences. Facilities management is a profession that encompasses multiple disciplines to ensure top functionality of the built environment by integrating people, place, process and technology (IFMA, 2016).

In Nigeria, facilities management has a history that dates back to as far as the colonial era where the Public Works Department (PWD) developed and managed public facilities (Lawrence & Oluwabamise, 2025). Some years after independence, the boom in national earnings occasioned by the 1973 oil exploitation and exportation gave Nigeria an opportunity for massive infrastructural development by the various levels of government. Unfortunately, the development was not accompanied by efforts to manage and maintain the facilities, hence the deterioration began soon after commissioning. (Adeyemi et al, 2020). Onwuanyi & Chima (2024) stated that the practice of facility management began in 1993 in Nigeria, when it was made the central theme of discussion at the annual conference of the Nigerian Institution of Estate Surveyors and Valuers (NIESV). They posited further that the conference aroused consciousness in the minds of the real estate professionals who had always been referred to as experts in property management. Roger (2017) indicated that facilities management, being broad, is a multidisciplinary profession requiring both technical and management skills.

The importance of user satisfaction in facilities management practice cannot be overemphasized. This is because performance evaluation of facilities is usually done by the end-users. Dejacó et al. (2017) iterated that building services assessment and condition monitoring need to be carried out to determine the status of services provided to the users. User satisfaction is a vital element used by decision makers to measure the capability of a facility to perform its functions and in the process, give comfort to its users. Therefore,

performance evaluation analyzed through user satisfaction aims to bridge the gap and establish the relationship between the internal measures that are the causes and the external measures that are the effects (Syarif, 2019). The efficiency and effectiveness of an organization's maintenance systems determine its success and survivability (Akinwande, 2018).

Higher institutions are faced with the pressure to improve the quality of facilities as well as their associated services. According to Hossain et al. (2018), private universities are striving to maintain the quality of education, so the evaluation of customers' perception is essential to provide motivation for and to give feedback on the effectiveness of educational plans and implementation for them. Essentially, facilities provide support and comfort for human resources for the attainment of the organizational goals and in universities, one of the important goals is to attract the best students and retain quality staff (Oladokun, 2019). Over the years, user satisfaction has become a major key performance index used in measuring the efficiency and effectiveness of the services rendered in facilities so as to ensure adequate performance and functionality. Al-Amri et al., (2020) opined that tertiary educational institutions have recognized that higher or advanced education is a service industry and so, are emphatically dealing with meeting the needs of their customers and stakeholders. In a university environment, however, there are many groups that can be categorized or classified as clients, these include the employees, students, families and society, and so, the concept of customer has not yet been clearly defined ((Nardelli & Rajala, 2018)). However, the primary customers or users in a higher institution are the students. This is because, the institution is built mainly for the students' capacity building and comfort, while the secondary customers are employees which constitute teaching and non-teaching members of staff. Staff and students are retained when they are

satisfied with the functionality of the facilities and services rendered in an institution (Weerasinghe & Fernando, 2018).

As defined by Ojoajogu et al., (2021), satisfaction is a state felt by a person who has experienced a performance or an outcome that fulfills his or her expectations. Satisfaction is a function of relative level of expectations and perceived performance (Hossain et al., 2018). User satisfaction of facilities is important in higher institutions for the stakeholders, employees, and students because of a range of reasons which can be categorized under sub-headings viz; ratings and rankings and comfort. Usually, a survey is used to determine user satisfaction and the analysis of the feedback is used to improve the facilities. Yusuf and Ibrahim (2024) opined that the facilities resources of the university and their management play important roles in achieving the goals of the university by providing the users with versatile, flexible and comfortable learning environments and an effective infrastructure as a basis for the university's functions.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Concept of Facilities Management

Facilities management is commonly defined as the establishment of an environment that supports an organization's basic functions by integrating service infrastructure to provide quality and value for money (Myeda et al., 2023). The British Institute of Facilities Management describes it as the integration of the physical workplace with an organization's people and operations. According to van der Voordt (2017), facilities management includes real estate, financial, change, human resource, health and safety, and contract management, in addition to maintenance. It represents a comprehensive strategy to managing, maintaining, enhancing, and adapting buildings and infrastructure to successfully meet organisational goals.

Nicholls & Crompton (2018) speculated that there are a number of factors or attributes that affect property values. There are structural attributes, neighbourhood attributes, time-related attributes and some others. However, it should be noted that these attributes are basic elements considered by users to rate their satisfaction and the efficiency of facilities services. However, a mass literature review indicated that little or no research has been conducted on employee satisfaction with facilities in higher institutions. It is against this backdrop that this study sets out to measure employee satisfaction of facilities services within an institutional environment, using selected buildings in Covenant University located in Ota in Southwestern Nigeria. In view of this, the following are the research questions for the study.

1. What facilities services are being rendered in the studied buildings?
2. What is the level of employee satisfaction with the FM services being rendered?

The discipline integrates several services to assure the operation, safety, comfort, and efficiency of buildings, infrastructure, and real estate assets. Core components include operations and maintenance, communications, emergency and business continuity planning, sustainability practices, hospitality services, ergonomics, project management, and property management (Zhou et al., 2024). Beyond cost savings and improved employee performance, facilities management frequently entails partial or whole outsourcing arrangements. It connects three interrelated domains: employees (human and sociological dimensions), work activities (performance and finance), and the work environment (architectural and engineering characteristics) (Xiong et al., 2022). Importantly, facility management necessitates long-term planning and a user-

centric approach. It should not be relegated to regular construction operations, but rather integrated into the planning stages of investment and development processes (Potkany, 2015).

Facilities Management Areas of Practice

Cheong et al. (2017) emphasise the importance of practical experience in addition to knowledge and skills for efficient facilities management. The International Facility Management Association (IFMA) 2009 Global Job Task Analysis identified eleven core competencies in 62 countries: communication, quality, technology, operations and maintenance, human factors, finance and business, emergency planning and business continuity, leadership and strategy, real estate and property management, project management, and environmental stewardship and sustainability. Communication entails conveying meaning via vocal, nonverbal, and mediated means (Fatimayin, 2018). It promotes coordination, decision-making, and morale (Kabulovich, 2025) and is required for effective leadership and stakeholder participation (Stefan, 2015; Okappy, 2018; Reagan, 2020).

Quality in facilities management is defined using numerous techniques (Myeda et al., 2023) and is related to customer satisfaction and continual improvement via Quality Management Systems (Kabulovich, 2025). Performance is frequently evaluated on physical, functional, and financial dimensions (Amos et al., 2019). Technology has both physical and informational components (Marmo et al., 2019) and improves competitiveness when matched with professional principles (Aziz et al., 2016; Adama & Michell, 2017, 2018; Ware et al., 2017). Operations and maintenance maintain the lifespan performance of facilities (Zurairhana et al., 2016), whilst human aspects address user happiness during

organisational change (Koilkonda, 2024). Finance, emergency preparedness, and business continuity are critical components of resilience (RICS Guidance Notes, n.d.; Canadian Centre for Occupational Health and Safety, 2020; Fadahunsi et al., 2019). Leadership and strategy determine long-term direction (Koilkonda, 2024). Real estate and sustainability functions improve asset value and environmental performance (Newell and Marzuki, 2022).

Facilities Management Practice in Nigerian Higher Institutions

Adequate maintenance of university facilities is critical to preserving institutional purpose and asset value. However, many Nigerian higher education institutions are deteriorating and providing poor service, which can be linked partly to a lack of maintenance culture (Ayoko et al., 2023). Asiabaka (2008) defined facilities management as the process by which organisations create and maintain structures to fulfil changing objectives. Effective facilities management at universities supports academic performance by providing and maintaining adequate teaching, learning, and working environments (Mahmoud et al., 2024). Tertiary universities have a wide range of facilities, including academic and non-academic buildings, sports and recreational areas, roadways, utilities, ICT infrastructure, safety systems, and specialised services (Fadahunsi et al. 2019). Users and facility management teams must collaborate to ensure seamless service delivery. Uko (2015) defined five essential stages of school facility management: provision, utilisation, maintenance, improvement, and auditing, emphasising that effective management improves staff productivity and student success.

Empirical research identifies structural and performance concerns. In a multi-campus study, Christensen and Nilsen (2021)

discovered differences in consultation, reporting, and response despite meeting cost and time delivery targets. Ikediashi and Aigbavboa (2019) recognised the increasing use of outsourcing in Nigerian public universities, but they also highlighted a lack of study on risk management strategies. Odediran et al. (2015) highlighted degradation, technological level, and funding as important influencing factors, whereas Oyedeji (2018) found variances in user satisfaction associated with funding and institutional policies. Notably, existing surveys focus mostly on students, with little attention paid to employee satisfaction with facilities services.

Determinants of Employee Satisfaction with Facilities Services in Higher Institutions

Infrastructure facilities have a substantial impact on university performance because they provide safe and suitable working environments for staff (Mbazor et al., 2018). Despite this, many Nigerian institutions continue to have problems in the quality and quantity of facilities services provided to staff and students (Yusuf & Ibrahim, 2024). According to Vakili et al. (2013), educational facility planning and design have a direct impact on institutional performance; nonetheless, difficulties such as overcrowded classrooms, inadequate staff housing, and restricted learning resources persist. University surroundings support both teaching and research activities, therefore well-maintained and functional facilities are required to ensure productivity and educational quality (Mbazor et al., 2018). Reliable water and energy supply, suitable convenience amenities, acceptable office sizes, sufficient lecture halls and laboratories, functioning office equipment and strategic building location are all important factors in workplace effectiveness. Dullah et al. (2023) argued that suitable work conditions increase employee productivity. Existing research

identifies a wide range of facility services that influence employee satisfaction, including lighting, furniture, noise control, indoor air quality, office space adequacy, HVAC systems, security, janitorial services, parking, mechanical and civil works, aesthetics, landscaping, fire safety systems, water supply, electricity, and internet access. These variables, taken together, form a comprehensive framework for assessing employee satisfaction with facilities services in higher education institutions.

Measuring Employee Satisfaction with Facilities Services in Higher Institutional

Existing literature describes recognised frameworks for assessing service quality from the user's perspective, including SERVQUAL and SERVPERF. Although these models are commonly used to measure student satisfaction in higher education, they are also important for evaluating staff satisfaction and were used in this study.

SERVQUAL: Higher education service quality has received policy attention, notably in Sub-Saharan Africa, where governments aim to improve educational delivery (Ankomah et al., 2005; Mensah, 2015). Jankalová (2016) defined service quality as a global assessment of service excellence, based on Oliver's disconfirmation model, which views quality as the difference between expectations and perceived performance (Forero & Gómez, 2017). They established five SERVQUAL dimensions: tangibles (physical facilities and equipment), responsiveness (timely assistance), dependability (dependable performance), assurance (competence and credibility), and empathy (accessible and comprehension of user needs). These characteristics provide a formal framework for assessing university facilities services.

SERVPERF: Performance refers to the quality of operation and the extent to which

facilities serve their intended purpose (Ikediashi, 2024). Given the high asset value and operating expenses associated with facilities, performance monitoring has become an essential component of facilities management. Wellalage and Reddy (2020) identified reinvestment patterns as cost drivers, whereas Amos et al. (2019) emphasised performance monitoring in facilities strategy. Performance evaluation enhances learning, planning, and design (Martínez-Caro, 2015). Satisfaction surveys, in particular, allow facilities managers to analyse the impact of services on productivity and plan for future improvements.

METHODOLOGY

In order to ensure an adequately scientific study, the researchers adopted the quantitative research method along with the use of a structured questionnaire. The adopted research design here is exploratory, utilizing the survey approach. The study population consisted of employees at Covenant University from the College of Management and Social Sciences and the College of Leadership and Development Studies. Participants were selected purposively because they are directly involved in or affected by facilities services, making them appropriate for evaluating satisfaction levels. A sample size of 133 was adopted, derived from a population of 199 using a 95% confidence level and a 5% margin of error. This ensured that the sample was representative while maintaining feasibility for data collection.

The satisfaction survey questionnaire was divided into sections capturing demographic characteristics, while other sections included closed-ended questions in the form of a Likert scale to assess employee satisfaction with facilities services. The questionnaires were self-administered and retrieved in the

same way to ensure completeness and reliability of responses. Data analysis was performed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS), employing tools such as frequencies, percentages, and the Relative Agreement Index. This analytical approach enabled the researchers to summarize responses systematically, identify trends, and measure employee perceptions of facilities services within the selected colleges.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Profile of Respondents

The socio-demographic profile of Covenant University staff in Table 1 above provides crucial context for understanding employee satisfaction with facilities services, as factors such as age, gender, marital status, nationality, employment category, education, income, and office typology influence service expectations, usage patterns, and perceptions (Adeyemi et al., 2020; Jensen, 2011). The workforce is largely economically active and professionally mature, with 85.1% holding qualifications above HND/B.Sc., 73.6% being teaching staff, and a majority earning between ₦601,000 and ₦1,800,000 annually, suggesting that respondents are discerning users of facilities and highly sensitive to environmental quality, maintenance, and service responsiveness (Frontczak et al., 2012; Kim et al., 2019; Price et al., 2011; Judge et al., 2010). Gender distribution is nearly balanced, enhancing inclusivity in satisfaction assessment, while marital status, predominantly married (62.8%), indicates attention to work–life balance and support services (Brunia et al., 2016; Hameed & Amjad, 2009; Clark, 1997). The respondent pool is mostly Nigerian (97.5%), reflecting local expectations in evaluating facilities (Loosemore & Phua, 2011), and staff are drawn from CMSS (60.3%) and CLDS (39.7%), highlighting discipline-specific facility needs (Nutt & McLennan, 2000). Finally, 67.8% occupy private offices, which

Table 1: Profile of Respondents

Variables	Frequency	Percentages (%)
Age of respondents		
18-25	0	0
26-35	49	40.5
36-50	54	44.6
50 years and above	18	14.9
Total	121	100
Gender		
Male	66	54.5
Female	55	45.5
Total	121	100
Marital Status		
Single	40	33.1
Married	76	62.8
Divorced	0	0
Widowed	5	4.1
Total	121	100
Respondent's Nationality		
Nigerian	118	97.5
Non-Nigerian	3	2.5
Total	121	100
Respondents Employment Status		
Teaching staff	89	73.6
Non-teaching staff	32	26.4
Total	121	100
Respondent's Educational Level		
Below HND/B.Sc.	4	3.3
HND/B.Sc.	14	11.6
Above HND/B.Sc.	103	85.1
Total	121	100
Respondent's College within the Study		
CMSS	73	60.3
CLDS	48	39.7
Total	121	100
Income Band p.a. (₦)		
85,000-180,000	2	1.7
181,000-600,000	22	18.2
601,000-1,800,000	62	51.2
Above 1,800,000	35	28.9
Total	121	100
Office Types		
Private office	82	67.8
Shared office	39	32.2
Total	121	100

Source: Authors' Fieldwork (2025)

may contribute to relatively higher satisfaction levels due to privacy and comfort, whereas shared-office users may be

more sensitive to issues such as acoustics, ventilation, and space adequacy (De Croon et al., 2005; Shohet & Lavy, 2017).

Level of Awareness

The level of awareness of facilities management (FM) services among employees is a critical determinant of service utilization, perception of service quality, and overall satisfaction in higher educational institutions. Awareness shapes how

employees interact with facilities systems, report faults, comply with usage guidelines, and evaluate institutional support services. In the context of Covenant University, Ota, the assessment of respondents' awareness of FM services provides an essential backdrop for understanding satisfaction outcomes and perceived service effectiveness.

Figure 1: Level of Awareness of FM Services

The level of awareness of facilities management (FM) services among Covenant University staff in Figure 1 above is notably high, reflecting familiarity with maintenance, utilities, space allocation, safety, and general campus infrastructure support, which aligns with the structured FM systems typical of private universities (Amaratunga & Baldry, 2003). High awareness is a prerequisite for informed satisfaction judgments, as users can evaluate service quality only when knowledgeable about service processes and standards (Parasuraman et al., 1988; Jensen, 2011), and it is reinforced by the staff's high educational attainment, professional orientation, and frequent interaction with FM services (Price et al., 2011). Effective institutional communication through orientation, digital platforms, and help-desk systems further enhances visibility and accessibility of FM services (Alexander &

Brown, 2006), encouraging participation, feedback, and adherence to protocols, which supports service efficiency and sustainability (Elmualim et al., 2010). While awareness may raise expectations and critical scrutiny of service performance (Shohet & Lavy, 2017), it also fosters perceived organizational support, commitment, and alignment with institutional values (Rhoades & Eisenberger, 2002), positioning Covenant University as an outlier in the Nigerian context where public institutions often face low FM visibility and employee dissatisfaction (Adeyemi et al., 2020). Overall, the high awareness level provides a solid foundation for informed satisfaction assessments and underscores the strategic importance of FM in enhancing academic productivity, staff wellbeing, and institutional performance.

End-user Levels of satisfaction with FM Services

Table 2: End-user Level of Satisfaction

FM Services	Mean	RAI	Rank
Car parking	4.00	0.80	1 st
Cleaning	3.94	0.79	2 nd
Waste management	3.94	0.79	2 nd
Water supply	3.92	0.78	4 th
Lighting	3.80	0.76	5 th
Security	3.74	0.75	6 th
Aesthetics (landscaping-mowing of grass and shrubs)	3.74	0.75	6 th
Road maintenance	3.56	0.71	8 th
Adequate office space	3.32	0.66	9 th
Fire alarm/fire safety	3.21	0.64	10 th
Mechanical works (air conditioning, plumbing)	3.16	0.63	11 th
Lift and escalator maintenance	3.13	0.63	11 th
Electricity supply	4.11	0.62	13 th
Civil works (masonry, painting, carpentry, office furniture)	3.06	0.61	14 th
Termite treatment	2.84	0.57	15 th

Source: Authors' Fieldwork (2025)

End-user satisfaction at Covenant University indicates generally positive perceptions of facilities management (FM) services, with higher satisfaction reported for routinely visible and frequently used services such as car parking (mean 4.00, RAI 0.80), cleaning and waste management (mean 3.94, RAI 0.79), and water supply (mean 3.92, RAI 0.78), reflecting effective planning, hygiene practices, and basic utility management (Jensen, 2011; Shohet & Lavy, 2017; Al-Hussein et al., 2015; Price & Pitt, 2018; Elmualim et al., 2010; Oladapo, 2016). Moderate satisfaction was observed for lighting, security, aesthetics, road maintenance, and office space (RAIs 0.66–0.76), while services that are technical,

preventive, or less visible—such as fire safety, mechanical systems, civil works, and termite control—received lower ratings (RAIs 0.57–0.64), highlighting gaps in responsiveness, preventive maintenance, and user awareness (Boyce, 2014; Al-Khafaji et al., 2019; Lottrup et al., 2013; De Croon et al., 2005; Proulx et al., 2018; Shohet & Lavy, 2017). Overall, the pattern suggests that employee satisfaction is shaped by immediacy, visibility, and service reliability, underscoring the need for a balanced FM strategy that maintains high-performing areas while improving preventive, technical, and safety-related services (Jensen, 2011).

Frequency of Complaints on FM Services

Table 3: Frequency of Complaints on FM Services

FM Services	Mean	RAI	Rank
Mechanical works (Air conditioning, plumbing)	3.55	0.71	1 st
Civil works (masonry, painting, carpentry, office furniture)	3.36	0.67	2 nd
Cleaning	3.11	0.62	3 rd
Illumination	3.07	0.61	4 th
Security	2.88	0.58	5 th
Electricity supply	2.74	0.55	6 th
Termite treatment	2.72	0.52	7 th
Adequate office space	2.72	0.52	7 th
Road maintenance	2.72	0.52	7 th
Waste management	2.72	0.52	7 th
Water supply	2.68	0.51	11 th
Car parking	2.50	0.50	12 th
Aesthetics (landscaping-mowing of grass and shrubs)	2.47	0.49	13 th
Lift and escalator maintenance	2.46	0.49	13 th
Fire alarm/fire safety	2.28	0.46	15 th

Source: Authors' Fieldwork (2025)

The frequency of complaints about facilities management (FM) services offers critical insight into employee satisfaction in higher educational institutions, as facilities directly affect comfort, productivity, safety, and overall workplace experience. The findings indicate that dissatisfaction is most pronounced in core, high-contact FM services, particularly mechanical works (air conditioning and plumbing), which ranked highest in complaint frequency, reflecting their critical role and susceptibility to wear and system strain (Shohet & Lavy, 2017; Hassanain et al., 2019). Civil works and cleaning services also recorded high complaint levels, suggesting concerns about physical condition, aesthetics, and hygiene, all of which strongly influence perceptions of institutional quality and care (Amaratunga & Baldry, 2003; Price & Pitt, 2012; Noor & Pitt, 2009). Illumination, security, and electricity supply followed, highlighting the importance of lighting quality, safety perception, and reliable power in supporting effective work environments, particularly within the Nigerian context (Frontczak & Wargocki, 2011; Ali et al., 2018; Okorie & Musonda, 2021). Moderate dissatisfaction across

services such as office space, waste management, road maintenance, and termite treatment underscores persistent challenges related to space adequacy, environmental quality, and asset preservation (Riratanaphong & van der Voordt, 2015). Lower complaint frequencies for car parking, aesthetics, lifts, and fire safety do not diminish their importance, as these services significantly shape daily experience, wellbeing, accessibility, and life safety (Pitt & Tucker, 2008; Lindholm, 2017; Then, 2013). Overall, the pattern aligns with existing literature emphasizing that responsiveness, reliability, and proactive preventive maintenance are central to reducing complaints and enhancing employee satisfaction in facilities management within higher educational institutions (Shohet, 2006; Hassanain et al., 2019).

Discussion of Findings

The findings revealed that employee satisfaction with facilities management services at Covenant University was strongly shaped by respondents' socio-demographic and professional

characteristics, as well as their high level of awareness of FM operations. The staff population is largely mature, highly educated, professionally engaged, and predominantly teaching staff, indicating a user group with high expectations regarding workplace quality, comfort, and service responsiveness. The near gender balance and dominance of married respondents further suggest sensitivity to work environment stability, safety, and work life balance considerations. High awareness of FM services among respondents provides a solid basis for informed evaluation of service performance, as awareness enhances users' ability to assess quality, report faults, and engage constructively with service systems. Consistent with facilities management literature, this level of awareness likely elevates expectations, leading to more critical assessments of service effectiveness, especially in areas that directly affect daily work routines and productivity.

The end-user satisfaction results indicate generally positive perceptions of facilities services, particularly for visible and routinely experienced services such as car parking, cleaning, waste management, water supply, and lighting. High satisfaction in these areas reflects effective operational planning, routine maintenance, and consistency in basic service delivery, which are critical drivers of perceived service quality in institutional environments. Moderate satisfaction levels observed for security, aesthetics, road maintenance, and office space suggest that while these services meet minimum expectations, there is room for improvement in aligning them more closely with user needs and functional demands. Conversely, lower satisfaction ratings for more technical and preventive services, including mechanical works, civil works, fire safety, and termite treatment, point to gaps in preventive maintenance, response time, and system reliability. This pattern aligns with established research showing that users tend to rate highly visible

and frequently used services more favorably, while technical systems attract lower satisfaction due to delayed fault resolution and limited user understanding of maintenance complexities.

The frequency of complaints further reinforces these patterns, with mechanical and civil works emerging as the most problematic services. High complaint levels in these categories underscore their critical role in ensuring thermal comfort, functionality, and structural integrity, as well as their vulnerability to wear, aging infrastructure, and service interruptions. Complaints related to cleaning, illumination, security, and electricity supply highlight the importance of environmental comfort, safety, and reliable utilities in shaping employee experience, particularly within the Nigerian context where infrastructural reliability remains a challenge. Lower complaint frequencies for car parking, aesthetics, lifts, and fire safety suggest relative effectiveness or limited direct interaction, although their strategic importance for wellbeing, accessibility, and life safety remains significant. Overall, the findings demonstrate that employee satisfaction with FM services at Covenant University is influenced by service visibility, immediacy of impact, and responsiveness, underscoring the need for a balanced facilities management strategy that sustains high-performing services while strengthening preventive, technical, and safety-related systems.

CONCLUSION

This study concludes that employee satisfaction with facilities management services at Covenant University is generally positive, but uneven across service categories, reflecting differences in service visibility, technical complexity, and immediacy of impact on daily work activities. The socio-demographic profile of respondents, characterized by a highly educated, professionally mature, and

predominantly teaching workforce, alongside a high level of awareness of FM services, indicates that employees are informed and discerning users with elevated expectations regarding service quality, responsiveness, and workplace comfort. High satisfaction with routine and highly visible services such as car parking, cleaning, waste management, and water supply demonstrates the effectiveness of operational and day-to-day facilities management practices, reinforcing the importance of consistency and reliability in shaping positive user perceptions.

However, the findings also reveal persistent challenges in more technical and preventive service areas, particularly mechanical works, civil works, fire safety, and termite treatment, which recorded lower satisfaction levels and higher frequencies of complaints. These services are critical to functional performance, safety, and long-term asset preservation, yet they appear more susceptible to delayed response, system strain, and maintenance gaps. The high frequency of complaints associated with mechanical and civil services underscores the need for stronger preventive

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maintenance frameworks, improved response mechanisms, and sustained investment in infrastructure upgrades. Overall, the study highlights that while Covenant University demonstrates commendable performance in core operational facilities services, achieving holistic employee satisfaction requires a more balanced facilities management strategy that integrates user-focused service delivery with proactive technical and safety-oriented maintenance, thereby enhancing staff wellbeing, productivity, and institutional effectiveness.

Recommendations for Future Research

Further research work can be carried out to show how the levels of employee satisfaction with facilities services in higher educational institutions compares to the achievement of institutional goals, and thereby situate such works within the strategic long-term goals of similar institutions. In another way, studies can be carried out on which contributes more to the attainment of institutional goals between students' and employees' satisfaction with facilities services respectively.

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